

D8.7

Yearly Communication Impact Report

PROJECT	BBTWINS
PROJECT NUMBER	101023334
PROJECT TITLE	Digital twins for the optimisation of agrifood value chain processes and the supply of quality biomass for bioprocessing
PROGRAM	H2020-BBI-JTI-2020
START DATE	1 JUN 2021
DURATION	48 months
DELIVERABLE NUMBER	D8.7
DELIVERABLE TITLE	Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plan reviewed with Annual Impact Report
SCHEDULE DATE & MONTH	30 MAY 2024
ACTUAL SUB. DATE & MONTH	29 MAY 2024
LEAD BENEFICIARY NAME	REVOLVE
TYPE OF DELIVERABLE	REPORT
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	PUBLIC

LEAD BENEFICIARY NAME	REVOLVE MEDIA
Address	AVENUE PALMERSTON 3, 1000 BRUSSELS, BELGIUM
Phone number	+32 2 318 3984
E-mail address	info@revolve.media
Project website	www.bbtwins.eu

This project has received funding from the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101023334.

Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	4
2. Overview of the Project.....	5
2.1. Introduction	5
2.2. Objectives.....	5
3. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	6
4. Annex.....	7
4.1. Annual Impact Report	7

List of tables

Table 1 Updated List of KPIs as declared in D8.5.....	6
---	---

1. Executive Summary

Communication and dissemination are a central part of the BBTWINS project to ensure that the project activities, results, and technology are communicated to the relevant stakeholders in a clear, consistent and effective manner.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan (D8.5) identifies the main objectives for communicating and disseminating the BBTWINS project, the key stakeholders to be targeted, and the strategy for engaging with them to maximise opportunities for the project results to be exploited at a national and a European level.

This document is an annual report tracking the communication key performance indicators and their targets. First, the tables of KPIs are displayed below, followed by the impact report. This period is for M25-M36.

2. Overview of the Project

Bio-Based Digital Twins (BBTWINS) aims to develop a digital platform for the optimisation of agri-food value chain processes and the supply of quality biomass for bioprocessing. The platform will be based on ‘digital twins’ technology – creating a real-time digital replica of physical processes in the agri-food industry. BBTWINS will also combine Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning, the Internet of Things (IoT) and software analytics in this single platform.

With 13 partners in 7 countries, the BBTWINS consortium will be focusing on meat and fruit production, integrating the value chain (from crop to final product) and will define the optimal pathway for each feedstock to maximise efficiency and minimise losses – without impacting quality.

2.1. Introduction

The BBTWINS Yearly Communication Impact Report helps track the communication and dissemination of key performance indicators (KPIs) as part of ensuring a comprehensive communication and dissemination of BBTWINS.

Communicating with stakeholders is a key challenge, both to inform them of project activities and results, but also to ensure the uptake of project technology and ensure the project’s lasting impact. To facilitate this communication, the project will reach out to stakeholders throughout the project to raise awareness of the added value of digitalisation in agri-food value chains in achieving increased resource efficiency, as well as to highlight the potential of BBTWINS technology.

2.2. Objectives

The main aim of WP8 ‘Communication and Dissemination’ is to advance and enhance the impact and results of the BBTWINS project around Europe and beyond. To achieve this, the Communication and Dissemination plan (D8.5) puts in place a strategy to deliver project activities, engage stakeholders, and ensure the outcomes of the project are exploited. This overarching communication and dissemination plan also requires strategies for both internal and external communication.

The plan sets out a clear overview of how all communication channels, activities, and tools work together to engage with the relevant stakeholder groups. WP8 overlaps with all other work packages apart from WP9 Project Management.

3. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The KPIs of the BBTWINS project are there to provide direction to the communication and dissemination efforts. The KPIs listed below (Table 3) will be monitored internally, with impact reports created annually (deliverables 8.2, 8.6, 8.7 and 8.8) showing progress on reaching these KPIs (M12, M24, M36 and M48).

Table 1 Updated List of KPIs as declared in D8.5

<u>Dissemination Products</u>	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Press releases	2	2	2	2
Quarterly Newsletter	4	4	4	4
(# of project subscribers)	500	150	300	500
(Opening rate per list segment)	25%	25%	30%	40%
Media Kit	1			
Press articles/media coverage	5	5	5	5
Specialised press – feature articles	1	2	2	2
(# of views / print dissemination)	100	500	500	500
Peer reviewed Open Access publications	2	1	1	1
Joint private-public publications	2	2	2	2
Videos				
Introductory project video	1			
Project videos	7	7	7	7
Use case highlight videos			1	1
(# of views in total)			800	1000
Data visualization and digital journey			2	2
(# of users)			250	400
<u>Dissemination / Clustering activities</u>				
Stakeholder consultations	2	2	2	2
Workshops				
(# of events organised per year)	1		1	1
(# of attendees per event organised)	50		50	100
(# of views per recorded webinar)	60		170	220
Mid-term Workshop & Results Conference			1	
(# of attendees)			150	
Final International Conference				1
(# of attendee)				200
Event participation				
(# of conferences, workshops, pitch events, trade fairs, other)	10	10	10	10
Activities Co-organised w/ CBE JU projects	1	1	1	1

4. Annex

4.1. Annual Impact Report

Media Relations

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Press Releases	2	4	1	
Press articles/media coverage	20	10	7	
Specialised press/feature articles	1	2	2	

Scientific Publications

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Peer-reviewed open access publications	0	1	1	
Joint private-public publications	0	1	0	

Events

Events	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Events attended:	18	10	21	
Workshops/conferences organised:	1	0	1	
Activities co-organised with other JU projects	1	1	1	
Stakeholder consultations	0	2	2	

Newsletter

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Total newsletters	2	3	3	
Subscribers	102	164	169	
Opening rate	26.5%	33.5%	43.1%	

Videos

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Videos	2	9	9	
Total views	276	995	582	
Partner interviews	7	6	7	

Website Overview

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Total Users	1,448	3,848	1707	
Views	5,088	6,230	5,461	
Engagement Rate	30.41%	29.30%	45,95%	

Twitter

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Total Followers	104	142	173	
Impressions	10,156	4,393	16,440	
Engagement Rate*	3.6%	3.8%	9,35%	

*Engagement rates measure the likes, shares, and comments to evaluate content quality.

LinkedIn

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Total Followers	302	531	628	
Impressions	7,374	6,750	22,726	
Engagement Rate*	4.99%	10.8%	4.4%	

*Engagement rates measure the likes, shares, and comments to evaluate content quality. The scaling and methodology used for LinkedIn has been fine-tuned, providing a more accurate number.

